
Pedagogical Approach to Intellectual Disability in The Case of A Sexually Abused 'Teen Mother'

Drossinou Korea, Maria

Department of Philology, University of Peloponnese [Greece]

ABSTRACT: This document gives attempts to highlight the perspective from the meeting of the triptych of concepts referring to gender, mental disability and sexuality inside and outside the family. Education narratives in film attempt to understand identity as expressed through the teaching of social skills to children and young people with disabilities, with some films observing the applicability of the pedagogical methodology of special educational needs observation by tracing individual stories of people over extended periods of time in their lives. Our study, therefore, focuses on a certain case of a teenage girl with an intellectual disability who has been sexually abused by her father. Her mother called her by the "nickname", "Monakrivi", "Precious" because she had unique "hidden" talents, which she tacitly recognized but also applauded, when she consented to her daughter's sexual relations her with her husband and father. In order to understand the pedagogical consideration of the individuality of the sixteen-year-old student who attends a special secondary school, as well as the necessity of implementing the intervention program [IP] of special education and training [SET], the pedagogical tool [Targeted, Individual Structured Inclusive Interventions Programs of Special Education and Training TISIPI f [SET] was used. Based on this reasoning, the positive aspects of mental disability in the young woman were investigated by approaching the pedagogical view of individuality in this particular case study. The "deficient" pedagogical culture regarding the meaning of sexual abuse and the predictability in the behaviour of children and young people was also examined. In conclusion, the pedagogical view of individuality [I] is related to the family and to the wider society, the position of the person with an intellectual disability in the school classroom, the understanding of the rules that govern inclusion in the group of peers even if he has suffered sexual abuse, but also to any other group. Targeted, individual structured differentiated inclusion instruction lends itself to the training of his social transactions, encouraging the individual to take active roles for his life.

KEYWORDS- Special Education and Training [SET], Woman, Mental Disability, Sexual Abuse, Cinematographer

I. INTRODUCTION

The concepts of gender, mental disability and sexuality are examined in the narrative of mental disability in the film Precious. Disability often refers to children with antisocial behaviour who are often considered "sick" by society. This behaviour has its roots in the child's family environment [1] and the abusive way he grows up [2]. The image developed by such a child as "Precious" [3], is not accepted by the social environment. The pedagogical consideration of the individuality of the sixteen-year-old student who attends a special secondary school [4], as well as the necessity of implementing the intervention program [P] of special education and training [SET] is approached with the pedagogical tool TISI-[P]- of [SET] [5]. Contrary to what most people believe, social norms define the outside world [6], class at school, family, and society itself. The multicultural view of inclusion provides unclear data on the content of the tripartite concepts of gender, disability and sexuality according to Ratification of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities and the Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities [7]. Thus, the normal child, with the help he receives from his family environment during the early phases, develops the ability to control himself, to understand the content of the emotional boundaries that govern social transactions [8]. The antisocial person is often credited as ill, indicating emotional deficits in early childhood where the child was unable to develop a good "inner environment" to play, study and work. Therefore, if a child has not received love, affection and security from his family, it is very likely that he will have difficulty understanding the linguistic content of the rules and will be led to socially unacceptable behaviour. With the help of psychotherapy, providing a strong and stable environment with personal care and love, it is possible to address the delinquent behaviour of the hopeless, hopeless, sexually abused young African-American woman [9].

Pedagogical Approach to Intellectual Disability in The Case of A Sexually Abused 'Teen Mother'

Brief description of the research study

Intellectual disability (ID), often defined as a reduced ability to understand new or complex information known as mental retardation, is marked by significant limitations in learning and applying new skills [10]. The pedagogical view of individuality recognizes dysfunctions in the individual's social interactions with others that begin before adulthood and last throughout life [11]. Intellectual disability depends on health conditions, impairments, but also on the extent to which environmental factors support the integration and full participation of the individual in society. It is a generalized neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by functional limitations in adaptive behaviour. Mental functioning is defined as general mental ability, in intelligence, working memory, learning, reasoning, problem solving. Adaptive behaviour is denoted by the collection of conceptual, social and practical skills that people learn and perform in their daily lives with speaking, writing, reading, using money, telephone, moving in means of transport, sexual behaviour. Intellectual disability affects approximately 2 to 3% of the general population. 75-90% of people are registered with a mild intellectual disability [12]. The story is based on the book "Rush" by Sapphire "Monakrivi" published in Greek by Kastaniotis publications [12]. In the film, Clarice Precious Jones is an illiterate sixteen-year-old, invisible despite being overweight. Invisible to her father, who rapes her, and her mother, who physically abuses her, experiencing maximum domestic violence. For the state, it treats her as yet another lost case of Harlem, declared with the triplet "female, African-American and mentally disabled". The sexual abuse [14] is systematically concealed, until Precious, becomes pregnant by her father with the second child. Her meeting with the progressive and determined professor is decisive. This important woman teaches her to write about her life, but also teaches her how to make it her own for the first time [15]. Her teacher was California-born author Safire, who grew up on military bases in California and Texas and taught reading and writing to teens and adults in Harlem, Brooklyn, and the Bronx for eight years. The story is about the horrible, violent, inhumane world of Harlem, where the young, illiterate, morbidly obese teenager Clarisse Jones lives.

Necessity of the research study and brief literature review previous investigations

According to the DSM American Psychiatric Association [10] and ICD [16], three criteria must be met for the diagnosis of intellectual disability [a] below average mental functioning, [b] limitations in two or more areas of adaptive behaviour in multiple settings, such as communication, self-help skills, interpersonal skills and [c] evidence that limitations became apparent in childhood or adolescence. The diagnosis requires a complete assessment of intelligence and adaptive behaviour by a multidisciplinary team of experts such as psychologists, special educators, child psychiatrists, and other specialists.

Observation methodology with the Pedagogical tool:
[Targeted, Individual Structured Inclusive Interventions
Programs of Special Education and Training TISIPI f [SET]

According to Christakis, moderate and severe intellectual disability are diagnosed early, while mild intellectual disability becomes apparent in elementary school due to learning difficulties [16]. The diagnosis of mental disability is not only based on numerical calculations and scores of intelligence indicators, but takes into account the adaptive function of a person with the methodology of observations [17] of the special educational needs.

The most well-known intelligence tests include the Wechsler scale for children and adolescents, and adults, the Stanford-Binet scale, the Kaufmann scale, and the Raven's matrices. In particular, the Wechsler intelligence scales consist of verbal and practical skill measurement scales. Their administration is personalized and, essentially, they provide the "mental profile" of the examinee. Accordingly, the WAIS-III (Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale) suitable for measuring the intelligence of adults, the WISC-III (Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children) suitable for measuring the intelligence of children and adolescents (6- 15 years old)

Pedagogical Approach to Intellectual Disability in The Case of A Sexually Abused 'Teen Mother'

[16]. The necessity of the research study is presumed on the basis of previous research regarding the evaluation of the quality of adaptive behaviour with the observation methodology of special educational needs [5]. The informal pedagogical assessment [18], [6], [5] in certain skills that are important for the conceptual tripartite gender, intellectual disability and sexuality, is carried out according to TISIP of [SET] and focuses on individuality [I] according to the T-[I]-SIPof [SET] algorithm focus in the film, and observes the heroine "Monakrivi". The necessity of the research study is also presumed, based on previous research regarding the phenomenon of sexual abuse of children and adolescents [14]. What until recently seemed banished from thought is now considered to exist, described, discussed [20]. And as a society, we often look at the reality in horror, especially when it comes to girls with mental disabilities.

Figure 2. Pedagogical view of individuality [21]

Child victims of sexual abuse and exploitation suffer from multiple and long-term physical and psychological traumas, which follow them into adulthood [22]. On the other hand, in recent years the sexual abuse and exploitation of children on the Internet is an evolving phenomenon [23]. At the same time, new forms of crime, such as revenge pornography and sexual extortion, have proliferated online and must be addressed by taking specific measures by states [23]. After all, the founders of psychoanalytic thought, from Freud to Klein and Winnicott, have argued - as early as the last century - that the foundations for mental and emotional health are laid very early in a person's life and that the first five years of a child are decisive for his subsequent development [25]. The theory and technique of psychoanalytic interventions in young children provides the possibility of flexibility and adaptation, to different needs, which they offer [26]. Athanasios Alexandridis emphasizes the need for applied psychoanalysis for treatment and early intervention in families with young children.

The sexual abuse of children and adolescents is defined by different professional groups from a different point of view [27]. The Council of Europe [22] has given a fairly detailed definition stating that it is: a) participation in sexual activities with a child who, according to the relevant provisions of national law, has not reached the legal age for sexual activities and b) participation in sexual activities with a child when coercion, violence, threats are used or the abuse is done from a recognized position of trust, authority or influence over the child, usually within the family [1]. Sexual abuse of a child is one of the most traumatic experiences that a child can experience, it is a form of violence against children, including sexual violence, accompanied by other abusive behaviours, such as bullying, isolation, and exploitation, in other words it is also accompanied by emotional abuse of the child [28] [29].

According to the World Health Organization [16], 1 in 5 children (0-18 years) are victims of some form of sexual violence or abuse (2014). In 93% of cases the abuser is someone the child knows and trusts from the family or friends' circle. Child and adolescent psychotherapist Lida Anagnostaki states that there is no specific profile of a child who may be a victim of abuse [9] [26]. Of course, studies record some factors that increase the risk of sexual abuse of children, such as:

- female sex: girls are 2.5 to 3 times more likely to be sexually abused than boys)
- older age: older children (12-14 years old) are more likely to be sexually abused),

Pedagogical Approach to Intellectual Disability in The Case of A Sexually Abused 'Teen Mother'

- the adverse conditions of the family environment: when there are serious conflicts, losses, dysfunctional interpersonal relationships and/or serious mental illnesses then there is likely to be less supervision of the children and therefore there is a greater risk of sexual abuse. Children with complex learning difficulties and disabilities who are supported with unsafe pedagogical practices in the school, academic community and also in the family [15] [19]. And they stay unattended for a long time or by trusted scientists and caregivers are more likely to be abused. Substance and alcohol abuse in the family and the existence of domestic violence have a particularly negative effect [24].

-and the child's mental disability: children with physical and/or mental disabilities are more often victims of sexual abuse. Studies have documented that children with disabilities are almost twice as likely to be sexually abused than children without disabilities [7] [11].

Signs indicating that a child has been sexually abused [23] are expressed in behaviour through psychosomatic symptoms and refer to Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) [30].

So, according to the observation methodology [6] of special educational needs [5] and the checklist of basic skills, psychomotor skills [21] with learning readiness activities are recorded according to the pedagogical view of individuality. In the special education and training teacher's book as well as in the student's notebook, psychomotricity is discussed with educational games with fixed and mobile cards, with the children naming the parts of the body, there should be a clear name for each [see Figure 2].

It is appropriate for special educators as well as occupational therapists and carers, special education staff to talk about the private parts of the body, that is, "those covered by underwear" and to explain that no adult or older child has the right to ask to see, touch or play with them, even if that person is someone they know and like, because they are 'personal'. These discussions are targeted, individual structured, inclusive and as pedagogical interventions of special education and training TISIPof [SET] are repeated, when needed. The special teaching methodology describes a series of criteria on the basis of which and on the basis of the adult [teacher/parent/other]-child pedagogical relationship, the type of bond that develops between them is understood. This relationship is the most important factor that can reduce the chances that the child or teenager will experience situations of sexual violation and increases the chances of speaking up if anything has happened that is troubling them.

II. METHODOLOGY OF THE CASE STUDY

The Methodology of the research process focuses on a certain case [31] of a mentally disabled teenager who has been sexually abused by her father. Because, a case study is a research approach [18] that is used to generate an in-depth, multi-faceted understanding of a complex issue in its real-life context. It is an established research design that is used extensively in a wide variety of disciplines, particularly in the social and special educational science. In the research questions, the pedagogical consideration of the individuality of the sixteen-year-old student who attends a special secondary school is investigated, as well as the necessity of implementing the intervention program [P] of special education and training [SET]. The case study provides insight into situations that involve a specific entity or set of circumstances [32]. They can be beneficial in helping to explain the causal relationships between quantitative indicators in a field of study, such as what drives a company's market share. By introducing real-world examples as the heroine "Monakrivi", they also plunge the researcher into an actual, concrete situation and make the concepts real rather than theoretical. They also help the teachers study rare situations that they might not otherwise experience. Also, with the data which collected from the film "Monakrivi" the case study is in a "naturalistic" [18] environment and they are limited in terms of research design. Also, another limitation is that the researchers lack control over what they are studying with numbers, which means that the results often cannot be reproduced. Other limitations to case study revolve around the data collected and the interpretations. For these reasons, we care be taken to stay within the bounds of the research question to the Pedagogical consideration of individuality, which the case study of a "teenage mother" with intellectual disability and sexual abuse on is focusing

By introducing real-world examples, they also plunge the reader into an actual, concrete situation and make the concepts real rather than theoretical. They also help people study rare situations that they might not otherwise experience. Because with the data which collected from the film "Monakrivi" the case study is in a "naturalistic" environment, they are limited in terms of research design: researchers lack control over what they are studying, which means that the results often cannot be reproduced. Also, care must be taken to stay within the bounds of the research question on which the case study is focusing. Other limitations to case studies revolve around the data collected.

For this purpose, the pedagogical tool TISIPof[SET] was used. Based on this rationale, it is examined whether there are positive aspects of mental disability in the young woman by approaching the pedagogical consideration of individuality in the specific case study. The "deficient" pedagogical culture regarding the meaning of sexual abuse and the predictability in the behaviour of children and young people was also examined. Furthermore, based on the fundamental theoretical analysis, the data of the pedagogical view of individuality are presented, analysed and interpreted based on the individual, family and school history and the results resulting from them.

Pedagogical Approach to Intellectual Disability in The Case of A Sexually Abused 'Teen Mother'

Monakrivi, is an illiterate teenager, has been the victim of rape by her disappeared father, has had his child and is now expecting a second one, in fact it is an abandoned, abused child "who has become a mother". Clarisse is treated similarly by her classmates and the people around her. The nickname Monakrivi, by which her mother calls her, is more of a euphemism, since Clarice is against her will. With the thought that Monakrivi's behaviour is directly dependent on childhood or even infancy experiences where phobias, or problematic and deviant behaviours [33] are linked to experiences recorded in the unconscious [6] [33] we approach the story. Her mental traumas have stood in the way of normal development and prevent her from expressing in words what is bothering her in the family environment. Dolto refers to the case of a little girl who exhibited inappropriate and deviant behaviour and unconscious body image [9]. Therefore, the cognitive, emotional and social difficulties faced by teenager Clarice Jones are connected to her internalizations of everything that has happened in her life regarding the specific family environment and what has been engraved in her unconscious. The education of children with behavioural problem [34] s as happened in the case of Monakrivi can change her life when she learns to read, write and verbalize her feelings.

III. PRESENTATION – ANALYSIS – DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

The discussion of the pedagogical consideration of individuality in the case of the "teen mother" with an intellectual disability and sexual abuse recognizes the influences of gender stereotypes but abusive behaviours in data from individual, family and school history. It is an incestuous, psychopathic, and abusive environment that reproduces the "well-kept secret" of violent behaviour set in 1987, in the New York ghetto of Harlem with her violent mother, Mary. The issue of equality involved with abusive sexual toys [20] is discussed in the context of substantive gender equality, the prevention and combating of gender-based violence and also in the arrangements for the granting of Citizenship [7] [24] [35].

The family history is complete with long-term physical, sexual and psychological abuse, with two pregnancies in her history by her father, Carl. The domestic violence is expressed through verbal and physical violence by Monakrivi's mother. The family lives in poverty, on welfare, with "Mingo", Monakrivi's child with Down syndrome [8] [19]. The wretchedness and unhappiness of the "degraded" family environment causes discomfort and despair for the humiliating situation of the person, which in our case is the "Monakrivi".

In the school history, he gathers data with the development of Monakrivi's second pregnancy, which forces her to stop school. The principal of the "conventional" high school arranges to send her to an alternative special school, which he hopes will help Monakrivi change her life. There a social worker and the teacher will help her. Even hope is dimmed by the scenes where the girl imagines herself to be thin and beautiful, dancing with handsome men who admire her. The culture of the school helps her to verbalize her mental pain when Monakrivi decides to talk about her traumatic experiences, and she confesses them to the social worker, Mrs. Weiss, whom she meets at regular intervals. She is the first to learn about Monakrivi's sexual abuse by her father and that he is the father of her children. When she gives birth to her second child, she names him Abdul and, in the hospital, she meets John McFadden, a nurse who is kind to her and emotionally relates to him [3]. The culture of the school and her inspiring new teacher, Mrs. Blue Rain, teaches her to read, underlining the word "happiness", and to write words like "love," showing her that there are positive emotions beyond negatives he has experienced. After a violent confrontation with her mother, Monakrivi takes her three-day-old son from her mother's arms and flees her abusive home, stopping at a church and watching the choir sing Christmas carols. There to protect herself from the cold, she illegally enters the school where the next morning she is found frozen by Mrs. Rain, the teacher who helps her continue school and raise her son. The culture of her school teaches her that social skills exist and help people trust each other and interact, just as it did with the unknown teacher who listens to her with understanding and shows her that the world is not "alone". black nightmare. From there, another, more optimistic course begins, where even her problematic classmates help her.

When family culture returns to Monakrivi's life with her mother informing her that her father has died of AIDS she is suspicious of social skills and self-care. So, when Monakrivi later learns that she too is HIV positive, but luckily her son Abdul is negative, she deals with it with the new tools she has acquired from the school culture [3]. In Mrs. Weiss's office, Mother Mary meets the psychologist and is accused of covering up the sexual abuse of her daughter from the age of three [30] [36].

IV. CONCLUSIONS-SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, the pedagogical view of individuality [1] is related to the family and the wider society, the position of the person with an intellectual disability in the school classroom, the understanding of the rules governing inclusion in the group of peers even if he has suffered sexual abuse, but also in any other group [4]. Targeted, individual structured differentiated instruction for inclusion is offered "through special education" in the training of his social transactions, encouraging Monakrivi to take active roles in her life [1] [28]. Child sexual abuse [22] [20] [26] is recorded in behaviours, "strategies", that perpetrators use and do not evolve in the same way. Initially, the perpetrators try to gain his trust, make him feel loved, special, desired, unique. Thus, the child feels a special bond with the adult, which may confuse him when he is later asked to participate in sexual activity. However, "care" does not in any way refer to real tenderness and care. When in fact the perpetrator is the father with the tacit consent of the mother, a "friend" gradually convinces the child that his sexual behaviour is acceptable. The perpetrators then gradually progress

Pedagogical Approach to Intellectual Disability in The Case of A Sexually Abused 'Teen Mother'

to more invasive sexual conversations and actions that can range from caressing to penetration, while at the same time taking steps to ensure that the child will not disclose the abuse even if it is "born" by the incestuous relationship child. The perpetrators use their power to dominate, emotionally blackmail or threaten the child to keep the secret, while many times they try to make the child feel complicit, as recorded in Monakrivi's gaze.

On the first point, the family circumstances may favour the manifestation of abusive behaviours given that the vast majority of sexual violations occur within the family environment of the person with an intellectual disability. Something that seems to be difficult for us to accept because as a society we have a strong belief in the myth of parental instinct and the widespread concept that all parents love and protect children [2] [29] [25].

On the second point, the conceptual triptych "gender, intellectual disability and sexuality" also highlights sexual abuse outside the family context where many times the abusers have an institutional role of caring for people with intellectual disabilities [12]. They may work in schools, special care and education centres, boarding schools, sports teams, religious organizations, and other settings where children and adolescents are active [36] [21] [27].

On the third point, in our study, the abuse occurs within the family and the immediate removal of the adolescent "mother" from the maternal home is required in order to protect her from further abuse [1] [6]. In these cases, it is necessary to contact services that have an institutional role and can help, as was the case with the special school and the social worker and psychologist who work there.

Closing the pedagogical consideration of individuality in the case of a schoolgirl suffering from overweight, mental disability and sexual abuse based on the observations of Monakrivi's behaviours, we conclude in the film that this is a child-teenager who became a mother and remains traumatized, confused, afraid, ashamed of deficient social skills [15]. Her identity has been determined by the degree of trauma she experiences and depends on the type and duration of the abuse but also on the identity of the perpetrator who happens to be her father, which as we know the closer the relationship with the perpetrator, the more negative the effects of the abuse. After all, it is no coincidence that the most common diagnosis given to children and adolescents with a history of sexual abuse is post-traumatic stress disorder [36] [23]. They exhibit avoidance behaviours, over-exercising recovery and reliving of the traumatic event, but also depression, which is accompanied by a lack of pleasure, guilt, social withdrawal, fatigue, disorganized school performance and low self-esteem and learning difficulties.

According to the law [24], "the teenage mother" who is a victim of sexual abuse, presents complex cognitive, emotional and social difficulties, delinquent behaviour due to abuse, parental neglect and abandonment but also due to domestic violence, therefore belongs to people with special educational needs. When indeed, for long periods of time the sexual abuse of children was not perceived as abuse and lived with the conspiracy of silence [3] [26]. Because girls were systematically punished as if they were at fault if they reported any sexual violation. The feminist understanding of sexual abuse places it on a political basis and highlights the imposition of silence, which made child victims feel abandoned and alone, which has consequences as traumatic as the fact of abuse itself [15] [19] [27].

An important benefit of the contemporary interest in the rights of children and adolescent women is the "shrinking" of the taboo of silence as it emerges from the study of the pedagogical consideration of individuality in cinema. The "deficient" pedagogical culture regarding the meaning of sexual abuse of the teenage mother is understood as a continuum of gender stereotypes inside and outside the family.

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Table with acronyms

Special Education and Training [SET]

Targeted, Individual Structured Inclusive Interventions Programs of Special Education and Training TISIPIf [SET].

Conflict of Interest Statement

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

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Pedagogical Approach to Intellectual Disability in The Case of A Sexually Abused 'Teen Mother'

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Pedagogical Approach to Intellectual Disability in The Case of A Sexually Abused 'Teen Mother'

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